

SHORT NOTES

Abnormal Partial Ionic Volumes of Some Tetra-alkylammonium Ions in Water

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Substituted tetra-alkylammonium ions are large symmetrical ions of negligible surface-charge density and hence these should behave like other large cations, such as Rb^+ and Cs^+ . In conformity with this fact, these have been assumed to be unsolvated by a number of workers¹⁻⁴, the exception being the tetramethylammonium ion which is slightly solvated in water. As against this, these ions have been reported to behave quite abnormally in such physical properties as apparent molar heat capacity⁵, viscosity⁴, activity coefficient⁵, etc. The data on partial molar volume at infinite dilution, $\bar{V}_o^+$, of the bromides of these ions have been recently reported⁶ and the partial ionic contribution, $\bar{V}_o^+$, of the respective ions, have been obtained⁶, assuming the partial ionic volume of the bromide ion at infinite dilution, $\bar{V}_o^- (\text{Br}^-)$, to be 25.7 ml/mole. From the known radii of the different ions⁷, their respective volumes, V_m^+ , can be calculated, as for the other common ions, from the relation:

$$V_m^+ = 4/3 \cdot \pi r^3 N = 2.52r^3 \text{ ml/mole}$$

where 'r' is in Angstroms and N is the Avogadro number.

The amount of contraction of the solvent on solution at infinite dilution, ΔV_o , which may be called, for the reasons discussed⁶, "striction" for each of these ions, can be obtained as the difference, $V_m^+ - \bar{V}_o^+$. The values of the radius, r , the partial ionic volume, $\bar{V}_o^+$, and the 'striction', ΔV_o , for different ions are reported in Table I.

The 'striction', ΔV_o , appears from Table I to be appreciable and, excepting the case of tetramethylammonium ion, it increases with increase in radius of the ion concerned. Assuming with Frank and others³⁻⁴ that these ions promote ice-like structure, there should be expansion, instead of contraction, as in the large ions like K^+ , Rb^+ , and Cs^+ , since the formation of ice-like structure will result in a comparatively low density of the solution and hence a larger partial ionic volume, $\bar{V}_o^+$. So it appears that the idea of

1. Robinson and Stokes, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths Publications, London, 1968, p. 124.
2. Nightingale, Jr., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 1381.
3. Frank and Wen-Yang Wen, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.
4. Nightingale, Jr., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 804.
5. Devsnathan and Fernando, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, 58, 784; Lindenbaum and Boyd, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 911.
6. Wen-Yang Wen and Shuji Saito, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 2639.

*In view of the negligible surface-charge density on these ions, it will be unreasonable to refer to any contraction in the volume of the solvent on solution 'electrostriction' which is supposed to be due to high electrical pressure on the surface of the common ions. Taking into consideration the special structural make-up of these ions, the contraction may be termed simply "striction".

the ice-like structure formation is not in conformity with the contraction or 'striction' observed in these cases. In fact, Eley⁷ has questioned Frank's concept in the case of solutions of gases and of tetrabutylammonium ion.

TABLE I
Temp. = 25°.

Ion.	$r \times 10^8$ cm.	$\ast Vm^{\dagger}$.	$\ast \bar{V}_o^{\dagger}$.	$\ast \Delta \bar{V}_o^{\dagger}$.
$N(CH_3)_4^{\dagger}$	3.47	105.4	89.1	16.3
$N(C_2H_5)_4^{\dagger}$	4.00	101.5	146.6	11.9
$N(C_3H_7)_4^{\dagger}$	4.62	233.0	215.1	17.0
$N(C_4H_9)_4^{\dagger}$	4.94	304.1	277.3	26.8
$N(C_5H_{11})_4^{\dagger}$	5.20	373.5	339.0	33.7

$\ast$ Expressed in ml/mole

The recent conclusions of Mysels⁸ and others⁹ on the structure of water throw doubt on the ice-like structure formation hypothesis. The idea of the tightening of the hydrogen bonds of water molecules around these ions^{7,9} could be used to explain the contraction effect, i.e. 'striction', in these

FIG. 1

cases. A more plausible explanation seems to be, however, that the water molecules have high probability of getting themselves lodged into the large vacant spaces between the four spacial spokes, formed by the long alkyl chains (four in number) attached to the central nitrogen atom in the tetraalkylammonium ions on account of the latter's much slower rotational and vibrational movements due to their unwieldy structure. These ions, although spherically symmetrical, do not have the inert gas structure and are not compact; these aspects differentiate them from other large ions like Rb^+ and Cs^+ , etc. and appear to be responsible for their abnormal properties. Assuming with others⁷⁻⁹ that the alkyl chains promote the tightening of the hydrogen bonds around these ions, it is difficult to believe that this bond-tightening effect

7. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 35, 1421; *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 218.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3503.

9. Balazs et al., *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1969, 1, 147; Bovey, *Nature*, 1961, 192, 324; Florotii, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, 69, 261; Diamond, *ibid.*, 1963, 67, 2513.

of the alkyl chains will be uniform throughout the large surface areas of the ions. The areas, far removed from the axes of the chains, will experience negligible bond-tightening influences with the result that the solvent molecules opposite these areas (assuming ions to have an imaginary spherical surface) will enter the vacant spaces within the ions. In other words, the solvent surface opposite these areas will 'bend-in' or 'cave-in' into the vacant spaces; water molecules so accommodated will experience some weak attraction of the positive charge on the nitrogen atom and may be held there loosely. Thus the ion is enclosed in a sort of solvent cage of a 'bent-in' surface. The larger the ion, larger the vacant spaces and hence the larger the amount of solvent which will be accommodated. So the contraction, ΔV_o , should be roughly proportional to r^3 (some space being occupied by the nitrogen atom and four alkyl chains). This is amply supported by Fig. 1.

The formation of clathrates by some of these ions, the decrease in the partial molar volume, $\bar{V}$, with increase in concentration (which is an abnormality), and the appearance of a minimum in the $\bar{V}$ vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curve at higher concentrations, the viscosity of solutions of these ions, and other abnormal properties can all be explained on the hypothesis that the water molecules are accommodated inside these ions.

If one tries to fit in any one of the relationships, suggested by different workers⁹⁻¹² to connect the partial molar volume at infinite dilution, $\bar{V}_o^{\pm}$, with the 'striction', none of them is found suitable because the electrostriction effect, occurring in solutions in the case of common ions and taken into account in these relationships, would be negligible in these ions. Since these ions are very large and the surface-charge density would be almost zero, their volume should not be affected by presence of the solvent^{11,14}. As the 'striction' or the net volume contraction, is directly proportional to r^3 (Fig. 1.), one can write:

$$\bar{V}_o^{\pm} = V_m^{\pm} - kr^3 = 4/3 \cdot \pi r^3 N - kr^3 = 2.52r^3 - kr^3$$

where the constant 'k' is ≈ 0.26 (from the graph). So the final relation is: $\bar{V}_o^{\pm} = 2.26r^3$.

It is necessary to draw the attention to the fact that the values of r for different ions are only estimated values and so the analysis of the experimental data on $\bar{V}_o^{\pm}$ of these ions, as given above, should be considered as tentative until more dependable values of r are evaluated. In any case, the explanation suggested for the abnormal properties of these ions should be valid even if the r values are proved incorrect subsequently.

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11. Hepler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 1428.
12. Mukerji, *ibid.*, 1961, **65**, 740.
13. Benson, *ibid.*, 1963, **67**, 1194.
14. Powell and Letimer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **53**, 90.